

Tech-enabled Solutions for Bottom of Pyramid: Success Stories from India

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Abstract

The realization of self-reliant and prosperous India would not be accomplished if a major chunk of its population is left behind. Prahlad & Hart (1998) referred to this major chunk as “the bottom of the pyramid”. The needs and requirements of BOP differ significantly from those of other segments. To realize the potential of this major chunk of the market their needs and priorities need to be identified and addressed. For ensuring sustaining profitability of BOP, companies need to facilitate them to come out of the viscous cycle of poverty and deprivation. The focus should be on educating, empowering and enlightening them. New technologies are enabling lower-cost distribution models, with the use of technology like internet for things, products and services may be delivered to the hinterland, which otherwise would have been financially unviable. The research paper explores five cases where technology and the internet had not only made products and services available to BoP consumers but also made their lives better in many ways. As the topic of the research addresses the question “How technology and internet can help in empowerment of the bottom of the pyramid in India” it is quite logical to employ case study method wherein three cases are studied where technology has led to a better life for bottom of the pyramid. The first case is based on an initiative whereby a public distribution system tracking system facilitated by global positioning system(GPS) in Krishnagiri, a small-town bordering Andhra Pradesh and Karnataka improved the efficiency of the public distribution system, plugged leakages and benefited millions. The second case discusses a mobile based technology innovation, E-Mamta, an initiative of the Gujrat which led to reduction in mortality rate and better healthcare of expecting mothers and newborn babies. The third case discussed is about the opening of “Tiny Branch” by Zero Mass Foundation in association with State Bank of India in villages. The bank branch operates entirely with the help of mobile phones and finger scanners. With the help of the technology branches of bank have been opened in areas such as Naxal hit Dantewada and in far flung hilly region of Seiling in Mizoram, which otherwise were thought of as dangerous and financially unviable zones. The fourth case discusses how smart meters is preventing electricity theft and the fifth case discusses how technology intervention during Covid in education sector continue to make education more accessible and inclusive.

Keywords: Tech-enabled Solutions, Bottom of the Pyramid, Empowerment, Inclusion, India, Technology.

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1. Introduction

The bottom of pyramid (BOP) is the term given to those 4 billion people whose annual per capita income, based on purchasing power parity in U.S. Dollars is less than \$ 1,500, the minimum considered essential to live a respectable life [1]. Experts believe that there was tremendous opportunity at the bottom of the pyramid. Realizing the market potential of bottom of the pyramid, companies shifted their focus on it. They started targeting this untapped market with cheaper versions of their existing products. The terms like generic version, no frill model, etc. came into being. This approach had a major drawback as it assumed that the only difference between the high income and mid income group customers and customers belonging to bottom of pyramid was that of buying capacity, which was often not the case. The needs and requirements of BOP differ significantly from those of other segments.

In the words of G Sundaram, Vice President, Corporate Development, Godrej & Boyce, "it is unlikely that BOP consumers will use refrigerator to store frozen peas or butter". Thus, bringing down the cost of product simply by reducing the features is not an answer to the needs of BOP consumers. There is a need to study and understand the market segment and provide customized solutions to their problems.

To enhance the profitability of customer groups belonging to BOP efforts must be made to uplift them. The upliftment should take place in all aspects including education, empowerment and active participation in policy formulation. However, all this must have a business sense also. After all the purpose of business is business. Marketing low-cost products with high-cost business models makes little sense for most companies [1]

One of the major reasons for the divide between the haves and have-nots is the inability of the poor to access products and services. Access to products and services can be ensured for the consumers belonging to BOP by employing different strategies. Selling various products ranging from toothpaste to health drinks in sachets is perhaps one of the most successful ways of making things accessible to the poor. New technologies are enabling lower-cost distribution models, with the use of technology products and services may be delivered to the hinterland, which otherwise would have been financially unviable [2]. The research paper explores five cases where technology and internet had not only made products and services available to BOP consumers but also made their lives better in many ways.

2. Literature Review

Bottom of the pyramid has been often viewed as an unprofitable and uncertain market [3]. The marketers believe that BOP population does not have the buying power to justify investment. The low price of goods and services targeted towards them does not leave much scope for profits. It is assumed that the population is unaware of and unused to advanced technologies. These myths have kept BOP devoid of products

and services to a large extent.

To actively involve the poorest strata of the society, it is necessary to ensure access and availability of goods and services to them through innovation [4]. A report published by the World Resources Institute and International Finance Corporation observed that there is enough information about BOP markets, and sufficient field experience to justify more attention as well as business investment [5]. There is ample business opportunity in bringing more of the BOP into the formal economy and in improving the delivery of essential services to this large population segment.

Addressing the problems of the large, fast growing and diverse BOP market segment offers a big challenge to the business institutions as well as the government institutions and demands out-of-box thinking [6]. Serving the BOP market segment often requires awareness generation and market development. For example, companies manufacturing oral care products need to teach the importance of hygiene and cleanliness to the BOP market segment before promoting their respective brands. The inadequate facilities and appalling infrastructure are other constraints that need to be dealt with [7]. Projecting BOP as a profitable market segment in one's own organization is difficult (8,9). Due to these reasons BOP has remained underserved and ignored [10, 11, 12].

The BOP population is characterized by unmet basic needs (access to basic healthcare, water and sanitation, financial services, education, etc.) The condition is so grim primarily because of local monopolies, inadequate access, poor distribution and strong traditional intermediaries. According to a report, "The Next 4 Billion -Market size and business strategy at the base of the pyramid" published by World Resource Institute and International Finance Corporation, Washington D.C.[5]. BOP markets are often rural, especially in emerging countries like India, are poorly served, dominated by local informal economies and consequently relatively uncompetitive and inefficient. They starkly contrast with wealthier mid-market population segments that are largely urban, relatively well-served and extremely competitive.

Although BOP market is quite a challenging and underexplored market segment, the opportunities are immense. Technology can play a very important role in serving the BOP. Accessibility is one of the thrust areas in catering to the needs of BOP. Distribution networks in emerging markets are different and not well connected; India is no exception [13]. As C. K. Prahalad categorically highlights in *The Fortune at the Bottom of the Pyramid*, "Distribution systems that reach the BOP are critical for developing this market. Innovations in distribution are as critical as products and process innovations". In this research paper five cases are discussed where technology and internet have been effectively employed to make services available to the BOP. The paper also discusses how deployment of technology has also led to transparency and curtailment of corrupt practices.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research design

The methodology adopted for the research was CASE STUDY METHOD. The researcher studied five cases to explore the benefit of employing technology for the empowerment of the bottom of the pyramid. Case study research is conducted to gain in-depth understanding of a case set in real word context. The case study method may be defined as follows:

“An empirical inquiry about a contemporary phenomenon (e.g., a “case”), set within its real-world context—especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clear [14]”.

Case studies are pertinent when research is either descriptive or explanatory. The research is said to be explanatory when it aims to explain a phenomenon and attempts to find out why or how a thing happened. As the topic of the research addresses the question “How technology and internet can help in empowerment of the bottom of the pyramid in India” it is quite logical to employ case study method wherein five cases would be studied where technology and internet has led to a better life for bottom of the pyramid.

3.2 Participants

The research paper explores five cases where technology and the internet had not only made products and services available to BoP consumers but also made their lives better in many ways.

The first case is based on an initiative whereby a public distribution system tracking system facilitated by global positioning system (GPS) in Krishnagiri, a small-town bordering Andhra Pradesh and Karnataka improved the efficiency of the public distribution system, plugged leakages and benefited millions.

The second case discusses a mobile based technology innovation, E-Mamta, an initiative of the Government of Gujrat which led to reduction in mortality rate and better healthcare of expecting mothers and newborn babies.

The third case discussed is about the opening of “Tiny Branch” by Zero Mass Foundation in association with State Bank of India in villages.

The fourth case discusses how smart meters is preventing electricity theft.

The fifth case discusses how technology intervention during Covid helped in continuing education and thereafter making education more accessible and inclusive.

Every case is discussed under four headings: Background, Problem Statement, Technology Intervention and Turnaround and Challenges.

4. CASE 1: PLUGGING THE LEAKAGES IN PUBLIC DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM

4.1 BACKGROUND

India’s Public Distribution System (PDS) is the largest distribution network of its kind in the world. PDS is operated jointly by the Centre and the state governments. It has a network of 4.99-lakh fair-price shops, making it the largest in the world. PDS aims to provide

subsidized food and fuel to the poor. Food grains such as rice and wheat that are provided under PDS are procured from farmers, allocated to states and delivered to the ration shop where the beneficiary buys his entitlement. The Centre and states share the responsibilities of identifying the poor, procuring grains and delivering food grains to beneficiaries. While the procurement, storage, transportation and bulk allocation of food grain is looked after by Centre, the state government monitors distribution [15].

It is not easy to manage such a large and widely dispersed distribution network. There are many vested interests and intermediaries who with their corrupt practices, defy the basic purpose of the system. The PDS often find itself in the news for all the wrong reasons. With scams of magnitude of crores of rupees defaming the system, the government is under public scanner to run it smoothly and ethically. According to the SP Pal report to the Planning Commission — a comprehensive government report on PDS compiled in 2005 — over 36% of the budgetary subsidy on food has disappeared in the qualms of corruption and 21% reaches the above poverty line households. Of the estimated 45.41 million below poverty line households, targeted PDS has reached only 57%. The report identifies targeting errors and ghost cards/ bogus cards as the major challenges to the targeted public distribution system. These, as well as some other flaws in the delivery mechanism, have led to large-scale leakages (36.38%) and diversion (21.45%) of subsidized grains to unintended beneficiaries. Another report — the Justice Wadhwa Committee report on PDS compiled in 2009 — had indicated four major reasons for inefficiency in food rationing system: many ration cards under a single name, erroneous records, specious distribution and inadequate monitoring system. The committee recommended an effective and efficient monitoring system starting from the top to the bottom encompassing transactions at all levels and transport. The panel also observed that the system must be web-enabled as it would enhance the transparency of the system.

4.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Krishnagiri which is a small-town bordering Andhra Pradesh and Karnataka has been facing the problem of deficit of food grains and other essential items allocated to poor sections of the society through public distribution system. The shortage arises because of the large-scale cross border smuggling. According to the official data in 2010, over 30 trucks carrying goods worth Rs. 20 lakhs were seized. Rice which was to be sold at Re 1 per kg under PDS used to be smuggled and sold at Rs. 13 or even more per kg.

4.3 TECHNOLOGY INTERVENTION

The solution to the problem was found in Geographical Positioning System (GPS). The trucks loaded with food grains and other commodities for public distribution were fitted with GPS. The GPS was designed and manufactured by EI (Experience Innovation) Labs in Bangalore. These trucks would leave the FCI (Food Corporation of India) godowns. The GPS was connected to the main server to which

the officials have access. With the help of the GPS device the location of every truck could be traced. One could also keep track of the time taken to reach the destination, which was the various fair price shops. The real-time tracking software installed in the GPS, the trucks could be tracked continuously through a webpage. The moving trucks are indicated by green pointers and the trucks which are not moving are shown by red ones. The movement of the trucks right from the stockyards to the point where the commodities are distributed among the cardholders viz. below the poverty line (BPL cardholders) and above the poverty line APL card holders) is under the surveillance of officers of co-operative department. If the officer finds that a truck is stopped somewhere longer than usual or the truck is following a route different from the intended one, the field officer may be alerted to check the vehicle, and the driver of the truck may be contacted on phone. This is how the goods reach the fair price shops safely. In order to avoid any malpractice at the end of the shopkeeper, the administrators have installed electronic weighing machines at the fair price shops. To ensure accurate billing at the time of sale, a general packet radio service (GPRS) enabled handy billing machine is used. These machines have been installed by an organization, Coromandel Infotech. It prevents any manipulation in records. The machine prints the bill in local language i.e. Tamil so that the cardholder is aware of the purchases made by him and spurious bill is not generated in his name. The billing details are fed in the central database and reports on the opening and closing stock are generated on a regular basis. It reduces the chances of theft at the shopkeeper's end.

4.4 TURNAROUND AND CHALLENGES

In the words of V Arun Roy, District Collector, Krishnagiri, "there has been a noticeable difference. For example, when we go for inspection, we have advance information on opening and closing stock. That way we can check pilferage effectively." C Rangarajan, who headed the prime minister economic advisory panel under the UPA government appreciated the technology-based initiatives of states like Tamil Nadu, Chattisgarh, Uttar Pradesh and Madhya Pradesh to address the wrong practices marring the PDS. However, more needs to be done in this field as there are many challenges. The vested interests are trying their best to outsmart the technology and find new ways of smuggling the commodities meant for PDS. For example, in Chattisgarh the truck drivers have taken out the GPS systems from the trucks and fit them on the motorcycles. However, despite the challenges technology has done a lot in making the ration meant for poor reach its rightful beneficiaries.

5. CASE 2: E-MAMTA, NURTURING MOTHER AND THE CHILD

5.1 BACKGROUND

According to the UN report, India had the highest number of under-five deaths in the world in 2012, with 1.4 million children in the country dying before age five. The figures are distressful considering the remarkable decrease in the under-five mortality rate since 2000 in

underdeveloped countries such as Bangladesh, Ethiopia, Malawi, Nepal, Niger, Rwanda, Uganda and the United Republic of Tanzania. Where on one hand the global maternal mortality ratio (MMR) dropped by 45 per cent between 1990 and 2013, on the other hand India still accounts for 17 per cent of maternal deaths. The UN has laid an ambitious Millennium Development Goal (MDG) 4 -which aims to reduce Under-Five Mortality (U5MR) by two thirds between 1990 and 2015[16]. India would lag if the related socio-economic; maternal and demographic; and environmental determinants are not aligned with the goal.

In the words of Thomas Chandy, CEO of 'Save the Children', "We need to focus all services for maternal health and infant health, but we are not investing enough as of now. The services are not reaching the most marginalized sections of the society."

5.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Reduction in the health indicators like Infant Mortality Rate (IMR) and Maternal Mortality Rate (MMR) is among the leading challenges in public health domain in India. Three main causes of all neonatal deaths in India are: prematurity and low birth weight, neonatal infections and birth asphyxia and birth trauma [17]. Each of the major causes of neonatal deaths can be prevented or treated with known, highly effective and widely practicable interventions such as improvements in prenatal care, intrapartum care (skilled attendance, emergency obstetric care and simple immediate newborn care), postnatal family-community care (preventive post-natal care, oral antibiotics management of pneumonia), 24 and tetanus toxoid immunization. However, one of the major challenges before public health in India is unawareness among major chunk of population. Many deaths can be prevented if the expecting mothers are taken care of. Tracking pregnant mothers and children is the prerequisite for providing effective healthcare services to this group. This in turn can have a large impact on reducing IMR and MMR [18].

5.3 TECHNOLOGY INTERVENTION

E-mamta is a mobile phone-based technology application implemented by the Government of Gujrat since 2010. It is web-based software application accessed through <http://e-mamta.guj.nic.in/>. Under this program rural health worker, trained by the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) conduct door-to-door survey collecting information about pregnant women and mothers of newly born infants and send it using their mobile phone to State Rural Health Mission (SRHM). SRHM which is the government body, collates the data into a centralized database. System generated unique Health IDs is provided to such females. This data is then used to alert rural health workers - through SMS to ensure they keep on reminding the pregnant women and mothers of newly born infants of immunization dates and precautions to be taken and facilitate the process. In addition, timely SMS is sent to beneficiaries directly, if they have a phone, for uptake of services. The state office regularly monitors the data entry at each

facility. Reporting system has been developed to monitor timely registration of pregnant women and infants. Training is provided by state to grass root workers for name-based tracking of mother and child as well as for maternal and child health related issues.

To take prompt and timely policy decisions it is essential to look at the overall statistics of all the district level hospitals holistically. It requires an integrated information system across the hospital processes. The Health Management Information System (HMIS) has been developed to help the administrators to have better monitoring and control of the functioning of hospitals across the state using correct and timely data. It also assists the doctors and medical staff to improve health services with readily available case history of the patient. It ensures smooth workflow with less paperwork and formalities. It also alerts doctors through parameterized alarms and triggers during patient treatment cycle.

5.4 TURNAROUND AND CHALLENGES

The initiative has among its admirers Dr. Devi Prasad Shetty, founder of Narayana Health, a multi-specialty hospital chain in India, headquartered in Bengaluru. The business model of Narayana Health also accorded a place in the Global Healthcare and Harvard Business School Case Study. In the words of Dr Devi Prasad Shetty, "E-Mamta has been a great success in reaching out to rural families. In recent years, many developing countries have combined mobile technology with public health delivery to communicate with even the most remote person.

With the success in Gujarat, NRHM is piloting the model in other states. States such as Himachal Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Jammu & Kashmir, and Jharkhand have rolled out E-Mamta with the help of the National Informatics Council. The plan is to take it national eventually [19].

In Andhra Pradesh, the program is called Amma Lalana, which stands for mother's care in the local dialect. The program tracks the status of health of all pregnant women and infants through a mobile based system. In addition, it also to enroll these women to avail services of public health centers free of cost instead of having to pay hefty fees to a private hospital.

However, merely disseminating the health-related updates and information via SMSs to pregnant women and mothers of newly born infants may not be an effective mode of communication. The absence of local script support for low-end mobile phones is a major challenge. The messages sent are in the local language but typed in English alphabet. This may hamper the message to some extent. To solve the problem, Gujarat is considering sending recorded voice messages. It is easier to understand recorded messages chances for misinterpretation are also lessened. In addition, the NRHM is also developing an automated voice response system that will respond to the callers in their regional languages and may connect them with the experts through a mobile hotline.

The National Association of Software and Services Companies (NASSCOM), a trade association of Indian Information Technology

(IT) and Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) industry felicitated E-Mamta with the Social Innovation Honours Awards for its great potential in combining a network of trained health-workers along with mobile technology. E-Mamta may go a long way in ensuring a healthier and brighter future.

6. Case 3: BANKING ON THE BARREN LANDS

6.1 BACKGROUND

In India, making formal financial services and products accessible to all has been a problematic area for banking policy for many years. According to the report of a committee constituted by Reserve Bank of India, the Committee on Medium-term Path on Financial Inclusion (CMPFI), the number of branches per 100,000 of population in rural and semi-urban areas is still less than half of that in urban and metropolitan areas [20]. While demographic penetration has increased one-and-a-half times during 2006-15, the north-eastern states as also states such as Bihar, Jharkhand, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal and Madhya Pradesh are less penetrated in terms of the number of branches in relation to their population. CMPFI concluded that although a significant improvement has been observed in banking access, there is still a large gap in some regions for various reasons that need to be addressed. Such regions mainly lie in the north-eastern, eastern and central states. The banking facility in these areas is meager due to topographical inaccessibility and security concerns. Mobile banking can largely solve such problems. In some of the areas, mobile connectivity may not be commercially viable and may not attract banks and telecom service providers financially. However, the telecom service providers may be encouraged to use their corporate social responsibility (CSR) funds for this purpose.

6.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

State Bank of India wanted to open branches in the naxal-hit district of Dantewada in Chhattisgarh and the hilly region of Seiling in Mizoram. The market was untapped and had a lot of potential. However, Dantewada was a risky location for security reasons as it was a naxalite-hit area. Seiling, on the other hand, was a hilly region and had a scarce population. Therefore, a banking solution was required that was not only financially viable but user-friendly and foolproof as well.

6.3 TECHNOLOGY INTERVENTION

A Little World (ALW) is a company with a vision to "Touch a billion people through innovative technologies and alliances at the bottom of the pyramid for delivering multiple financial services at the lowest cost." ALW has many innovations to its credit. ALW runs a foundation in the name of Zero Mass Foundation (ZMF), which makes available banking services in far-flung areas and remote villages, under pre-defined service agreements with Banks and fulfills all front-end operations on behalf of the banks for ensuring financial inclusion at grass root level. ZMF manages the field force, account creation, appointment of Customer Service Points (CSPs), management of cash

and other logistics in such areas. For this purpose, ZMF collaborates with influential local organizations, district and state administration to ensure seamless functioning and operations. One of the praiseworthy brainchildren of ZMF is "Tiny Branch" which provide banking facility to places like Dantewada and Seiling [21].

The Tiny Branch costs just Rs 15,000 per installation and requires just a mobile phone and a fingerprint scanner. ZMF in collaboration with Nokia has designed a handset which can identify RFID tags for identification and tracking purposes; it also has an inbuilt application that helps in opening of new account and performing banking transactions. The phone can store data of up to 50,000 customers for a period of five years. The phone has a camera which can be used for taking pictures of the customer for making an account card. The name of the customer is recorded in his own voice as a voice tag, which is used for verification purposes to avoid any banking fraud. Enhancing the security a step further the five fingers are also scanned and the fingerprints recorded. This is in addition to the written details of the customers. The equipment can record details in 11 languages including Arabic.

Once a bank has identified a remote village or a far-flung area where starting a regular branch may not be possible because of various constraints it enters into an agreement with ZMF to open a Tiny Branch in such areas. ZMF with the help of the senior people in such areas or the Panchayat appoints Customer Service Points (CSPs). CSPs are equipped with mobile phone and fingerprint scanners and are given the responsibility to open bank accounts, spread awareness and popularize the concept. They are also entrusted to perform the banking transactions. The Tiny Branch receives the cash from the nearest local branch.

Lack of electricity is not an obstruction as the devices work on a battery that can be charged using a solar panel. There is no need for internet connectivity or for enrolling customers or carrying out transactions. However, transactions must be recorded on an hourly basis through GPRS. This is how banking services are made available to customers for whom banks were inaccessible earlier.

6.4 TURNAROUND AND CHALLENGES

In the words of Anurag Gupta, founder and director of the Zero Mass Foundation, "The Tiny Branch is one of our most important creations and I had to let go of others in order to concentrate on this." While the cost of installing Tiny Branch is low, Gupta is striving to lower it further. He targets to install 250,000 of these Tiny Branch's across Indian villages. This would make banking, insurance and other such services reach the un-banked population, which is otherwise unfeasible for the institutions to provide directly. Zero has enabled many villages and rural areas to overcome the menace of poverty and inequality.

7. Case 4 : STREAMLINING THE CURRENT FLOW

7.1 BACKGROUND

Power distribution in India is marred by the problem of electricity theft. People use different methods for

the purpose which include meter altering, unlawful associations, and bypassing meters. This unlawful or unapproved utilization of electricity without appropriate installment and payment, causes lots of financial loss to state-owned power distribution companies (discoms). In 2024, Uttar Pradesh Power Corporation Limited (UPPCL) flagged 37 of its 40 zones where the revenue recovery rate per unit decreased since the last year despite it selling 24% more energy to users during the same period. A recent report prepared by UPPCL shows that while the corporation has sold more electricity to consumers this year, it's per unit through rate decreased compared to what it was in the last financial year. The low through rate in UP is attributed to several factors including rampant theft of electricity, high technical and commercial losses and inefficient billing, among others. In the annual revenue requirement (ARR) for FY 2024-25, UPPCL has projected its revenue requirement to be Rs. 1,01,785 crore and the revenue (at existing tariffs) as ₹75,561.62 crore. Despite the state government's subsidy of Rs. 15,019.99 crore, the corporation expects a revenue gap of Rs. 11,203.00 crore in 2024-25. In these circumstances discoms find it difficult to invest in the sector. Therefore, research and development may take a backseat and opportunities may be lost.

7.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Power theft is a problem faced by all state-owned power distribution companies all over the country. Illegal electricity connections and theft of power lead to commercial loss which affects the financial health of the distribution companies with consequential effects like poor quality of power. Electricity losses are majorly divided into two main categories: technical losses and non-technical losses. Technical losses are the losses which are caused at the power stations or during transmission and distribution etc. Electricity theft falls under non-technical losses as they are caused by the actions of third party [22]. Further the Electricity theft can be categorized in different kinds as per the electrical equipment used to carry out this offence. Mishandling of electricity meter is one of the most widely used methods for electricity theft. An electricity meter, also known as an energy meter, is a device that measures the amount of electricity consumed by a building, tenant space, or electrically powered equipment. It's typically installed at the customer's premises by the power company. Meters can be used in different ways to carry out the electricity theft. Tampering of meters and preventing the mechanical disc from moving by sealing it, bypassing the meter illegally by connecting it to the fuse which prevents the movement of rotating disc and thereby preventing the recording of consumption of energy and opening of meter without damaging its seal and reversing the dials are some of the common methods used to tamper the meter. Electronic meters can also be tampered by a sudden electrostatic discharge which causes latent or permanent damage. Such acts have an adverse effect on the economy, as huge revenue losses owing to electricity theft amount to billions annually. In developing countries like India around 50% of generated electricity is lost through theft which result in scarcity in electricity supply and unsatisfied

consumers [23]. The AT&C (Aggregate Technical and commercial) losses range from 15% to 65% across India with an average of 34% annually [23]. Electricity theft disturbs the local area's supply of electricity, leading to overloading of transformers creating blackouts or brownouts. It also leads to damage of property and utility and increases the transmission and distribution losses due to tampering of wires and cables [24]. Heavy losses due to electricity theft have prevented the reduction of tariffs and subsidies provided for agriculture. Eliminating these losses are needed to improve the standard of living by allowing economically weaker sections to access electricity [25].

7.3 TECHNOLOGY INTERVENTION

As a solution to the problem, smart meters were introduced. A smart meter links an electricity supplier and user by providing information on demand and voltage. It helps discoms collect real-time data on electricity usage and faults. Users of smart prepaid meters, a variant, pay for electricity by recharging the meter-like they do for a prepaid mobile phone subscription. Smart meters help prevent electricity leakages and make billing efficient, reducing the aggregate technical and commercial (AT&C) losses of discoms. "Prepaid" gives an upfront revenue channel for discoms, which are required to improve their demand-side management. Smart meters also provide real-time data, which could be utilized to prevent power theft further. The Noida Power Company Limited (NPCL), the power distribution company in Greater Noida, successfully utilized advanced data analysis techniques to identify power theft amounting to ₹96 lakh. The deployment of high-tech data analysis tools has enabled the power discom to effectively monitor and analyze electricity consumption patterns across its network. By comparing actual usage with expected demand, the technique enables the company to identify discrepancies that point to illegal activities.

7.4 TURNAROUND AND CHALLENGES

Launched in 2021, the 3 trillion Revamped Distribution Sector Scheme (RDSS) aims to improve discoms' operations and finances. A major part of RDSS's first phase was installing smart meters. The overall target is to install 250 million smart meters by 2025. Discom's AT&C loss on an aggregate basis declined to 15.4 per cent in financial year 2022-23 from 20.73 per cent in FY20, according to a CareEdge report published in March. The first tenders to install smart meters were given out in FY22, starting in Uttar Pradesh and Haryana. But it is Bihar that has the largest number of smart meters installed. It has 3.1 million smart meters installed (National Smart Grid Mission). Bihar's efforts have helped as the billing of discoms improved to 83.11 percent in FY24 from 75.68 percent in FY21. AT&C losses reduced to 21.74 percent in FY24 from 29.77 percent in FY22. Revenue collection was 15,108 crores in FY24, making a 13.09 percent rise from the previous year. The incidents of electricity theft were reduced [26]. Smart meters provide automated, accurate and real-time data on electricity consumption, reducing human errors associated with manual meter reading. It also led to operational cost reduction giving more time to focus on customer service and

maintenance. The real-time data also gave an insight into the consumption pattern of power. Customers were also better informed as they received detailed information about their electricity usage, which inspired them to check their energy consumption. Energy consumption decreased in divisions where smart meters were installed.

Grid resilience and grid flexibility are the critical elements of any smart grid, which can be built through digitization in the grid led by smart meters. Success of digitization initiatives would depend on provision of adequate infrastructure and large-scale adoption by consumers.

8. Case 5: EVERY CLOUD HAS A SILVER LINING

8.1 BACKGROUND

India has the world's second-largest school system, after China [27]. During the COVID-19 crisis, one of the toughest challenges was to ensure the continuation of the education of children as schools were closed to contain the virus. Shutting schools to maintain social distancing during the COVID-19 crisis was the most logical solution to avoid community transmission in the initial response to COVID-19, given uncertainty over transmission rates among school-aged children and the potential impact of the virus. All educational institutions in India were temporarily closed in March 2020. As India went into lockdown at the end of March 2020, most schools were wrapping up the 2019-20 academic year. By May, amidst the upsurge in COVID-19 cases across the country, it became clear that it would not be possible to resume in-school classroom sessions for the new academic year. Therefore, new ways of imparting knowledge and education needed to be explored so that the future of the nation would not be at a loss.

8.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Since the national lockdown and school closure in March 2020, teachers have played a critical role not only in imparting education but in reaching out to the community as well. The teachers had to quickly switch gears to distance learning and improve their digital skills with little or no training. Issues such as the challenges of accessing digital tools by students and teachers, and the unmonitored quality of distance learning were also there. Many a time the students belonging to the lower strata of society do not have anybody at home to tutor and guide them. Their parents and elders lack such skills. Moreover, the young children may be provided with some help at home but as the level of class increases, such assistance becomes even less available. According to the ASER 2020 survey, close to three-quarters of all schoolchildren received school-related help from family members. This was more pronounced for younger children, with 82 per cent of children in Grades 1 and 2 receiving help from family members as compared to 68 per cent of children in Grade 9 and above. As expected, parents with higher education levels were better equipped to help their children than parents with lower educational attainments. Lack of digital devices, sufficient infrastructure, and affordability were other major concerns.

8.3 TECHNOLOGY INTERVENTION

In April 2020, the Ministry of Human Resource Development (renamed the Ministry of Education in July 2020 in line with the NEP) presented the Alternative Academic Calendar for Students, AAC guidelines on continuing formal school education online (NCERT Alternative Academic Calendar). The AACs are a set of four documents – one each for primary, upper primary, secondary, and higher secondary schooling – that outline measures for educators to ensure continuity in curriculum learning from the safety of students' homes through a blend of online and offline activities.

India's education sector has witnessed a surge in solutions to support the continued learning of students during the COVID-19 lockdown.

To support continuous learning while schools are closed, the Ministry of Education shared various free digital e-learning platforms in their press release [28]. The government has made a strong effort to create a repository of learning content and has implemented EdTech interventions in partnership with several NGOs such as EkStep, Khan Academy, and Azim Premji Foundation. Access to the following resources is free:

DIKSHA: Digital Infrastructure for Knowledge Sharing (DIKSHA) is an open-source national platform for learners and teachers to enable educational autonomy. Learners can access more than 80,000 e-books (including school textbooks for all grades) in multiple languages – the content supports homework and exam preparation with the help of 'question banks. Teachers can undergo training on the platform, access tools to help them with their lesson plans and content explanation, as well as assessment of their students. The content can also be viewed through a QR code on textbooks. This app can be downloaded from the iOS and Google Play Store. Website: <https://diksha.gov.in> or <https://seshagun.gov.in/shagun>

e-PATHSHALA: In this portal, the National Council for Education Research and Training (NCERT) has deployed 1,886 audios, 2,000 videos, 696 e-books (e-Pubs), and 504 Flip Books for Grades 1–12 in different languages. A mobile app is available. Website: <http://epathshala.nic.in> or <http://epathshala.gov.in> National Repository of Open Educational Resources (NROER): This portal has a total of 14,527 files, including 401 collections, 2,779 documents, 1,345 interactive, 1,664 audio, 2,586 images, and 6,153 videos in different languages. Website: <http://nroer.gov.in/welcome>

SWAYAM: Is the national online education platform hosting 1,900 courses covering both school (Grades 9–12) and higher education (undergraduate and postgraduate program in all subjects, including engineering, humanities and social sciences, law, and management). A unique feature of SWAYAM is that it is integrated with conventional education. Credit transfers are possible for SWAYAM courses (up to a maximum of 20 per cent). Website: swayam.gov.in

SWAYAM PRABHA: Has 32 D2H TV channels transmitting educational content on a 24/7 basis. These channels are available for viewing across the country using Doordarshan (the government-run

national television channel) free dish, set-top box and antenna. The channel schedules and other details are available in the portal. The channels cover both school education (Grades 9–12), out-of-school children, higher education (undergraduate and postgraduate), vocational courses, and teacher training in arts, science, commerce, performing arts, social sciences and humanities subjects, engineering, technology, law, medicine, and agriculture. Website: <https://swayamprabha.gov.in>

The education sector's response to providing continuing access to learning during school closures varies by state. Each state government is responsible for delivering a solution appropriate for that context. For example, Gujarat has focused on distributing QR-coded textbooks; Bihar and Uttar Pradesh have focused on learning programs on TV to expand access; Assam has been distributing worksheets along with midday meals to ensure continuity of learning; Kerala has also focused on textbook distribution and WhatsApp groups [29]. Odisha has turned to radio as online classes failed to reach all students due to poor mobile connectivity [30].

8.3 TURNAROUND AND CHALLENGES

The closures have affected millions of learners across India from pre-primary through secondary levels of schooling. Although a lot of digital content has been generated and transmitted to help children continue to learn from home, there is limited evidence on the extent to which this content is reaching children, whether they are engaging with it and the impact it is having on their participation and learning. The 2020 Annual Status of Education Report (ASER)40 survey was adapted to a phone survey format that could be conducted in multiple waves, to capture the effects of the pandemic on different aspects of children's education. It explores the provision of, and access to, remote education mechanisms and materials in rural parts of the country, and how children, families, and educators are engaging with these from their homes.

According to the UNICEF survey, the most-used channel for remote learning (by children aged 5–13 and adolescents aged 14–18) is WhatsApp: among students who have used at least one remote learning opportunity, WhatsApp is used by 47 per cent of students aged 5–13 and 55 per cent of those aged 14–18. The next-most used channels are textbooks (46 per cent and 42 per cent, respectively) and home visits by teachers (33 per cent and 31 per cent, respectively). Radio is used the least (1 per cent of students from both age groups) – most students do not typically listen to the radio, and radio learning content is often neither interactive nor tailored to meet students' needs. However, the government intends to reach the marginalized and remote student population (especially in the early grades) by expanding the use of radio and setting up 289 community channels [28].

9. Conclusion

Technology and the internet can go a long way in empowering people in India. Accountability, transparency, and accessibility are enhanced manifold with the use of technology. It can bring a revolution in India,

where many good policies are unsuccessful because of rampant corruption and red tape. The most striking feature of the five cases discussed is that in all cases, technology was used in a very simple manner. The success of the cases discussed lies in the smart deployment of technology. There is no rocket science involved in any of the cases. We need to think of other such applications, especially in the field of public services, where simple and everyday technology can change the scenario.

10. Recommendations

Technology must be deployed to enhance productivity, and the emergence of an egalitarian society where resources are made available to all. The future seems to be bright as the penetration of smartphones is on a continuous rise. According to a report by the Internet and Mobile Association of India (IAMAI), the number of smartphone users in India is expected to exceed 1 billion by 2025. The report also highlights that by 2025, around 56 per cent of all new internet users in India will come from rural areas [31]. This shift represents a significant change in the digital landscape, as rural regions become a major source of new internet users.

The emphasis should not be on inventing novel technology but on the benefits and value received. One of the major challenges would be to make people use technology. To remove their doubts and inhibitions and make them learn new technology. The process needs to be user-friendly. For example, everybody today can operate a mobile phone even though they may not understand the technology on which it works.

Deployment of technology would require a robust infrastructure. The government would have to do a lot in this regard. However, India needs to create an entrepreneurial environment where people may be driven towards technology-based solutions on their own. We need many more organizations like A Little World to bring a remarkable change in society. India has a young population that has a great willingness to accept technology. So, we have a demographic dividend working in our favor.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest to this work.

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